

Effect of Metal Ions on Bovine Serum Albumin-stabilised Emulsions with Particular Regard to Specific Flocculation Effect and Cation Binding

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The study on the effect of certain inorganic cations on petroleum (b.p. 120-80°)-water emulsions, stabilised by bovine serum albumin (BSA), shows that the cations bind to the protein surface under suitable conditions of pH and surface potentials, resulting in the specific flocculation of the hydrocarbon droplets. This specific binding permits evaluation of certain adsorption parameters, using a theoretical treatment based on the stability theory of hydrophobic colloids.

There is much evidence available in literature regarding ion binding by proteins. Such linkages are attributed to the electrostatic forces¹ of the ionogenic groups attached to the protein molecule, anions being linked to the positively charged groups such as H⁺ and NH₃⁺ and cations being bound to the charged COO⁻ and OH⁻ groups. The binding will, of course, depend on the valence of the ions. The phenomenon is of great biological significance. Many inorganic ions present in the body fluids are bound in a similar manner; calcium in milk is linked to the phosphoric acid groups of casein². Moreover, combination of foreign ions with proteins also occurs *in vitro*.

As regards serum albumins in particular, complexes with copper, lead, and calcium are known and have been reported by many authors³. The bridging of anionic macromolecular surface by these polyvalent ions results in the reduction of their surface potential by virtue of specific adsorption. If the system is hydrophobic, the reduced electrical charge finally leads to adhesion or coalescence⁴. Recently, Wilkins and co-workers⁵ have established the binding of Ca²⁺ and Cu²⁺ to the BSA (bovine serum albumin), coated over sheep leucocytes, though no substantial evidence for cross-linking could be obtained.

In the present investigation, an attempt has been made to study the binding of polyvalent metal ions, such as Ca²⁺, Ba²⁺, Cu²⁺, Pb²⁺, UO₂²⁺, La³⁺, and Th⁴⁺, to the BSA molecules covering the hydrocarbon droplets. Measurements of ζ -potentials and flocculation of the emulsions at suitable pH's in presence of the aforesaid inorganic cations indicate their specific binding and also enable us to calculate the binding parameters, using a theoretical treatment based on the stability theory of hydrophobic colloids.

1. Haurowitz, "Chemistry & Biology of Proteins", Academic Press, New York, 1950, p. 73.
2. Dieu and Bull, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 71, 450.
3. Anson and Edsall, "Advances in Protein Chemistry", Academic Press, New York, 1956, vol. 11, p. 311.
4. Davies and Rideal, "Interfacial Phenomena", Academic Press New York, 1961, p. 430.
5. Wilkins *et al.*, *J. Theoret. Biol.*, 1962, 2, 173, 186.

Calculation of Free Energies of Cation Adsorption

On adding small quantities of foreign ions (which in effect will not change the ionic strength), capable of being adsorbed or bound to the protein covering the emulsion droplets, the charge density will change and will be given by the Stern equation⁶ :

$$\sigma_s = \frac{N_1 \epsilon v}{1 + \frac{55.6}{C} \exp. (\Delta \bar{G}/kT)}$$

where C is the molar concentration of the added salt, N_1 , the number of the binding sites per cm^2 and $\Delta \bar{G}$ is the free energy of adsorption per molecule. This can be put into the form^{5,7}:

$$\sigma_s = \frac{k_1 C}{1 + k_a C} \quad \left. \begin{array}{l} \dots \dots \dots \\ \dots \dots \dots \end{array} \right\} \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

where $k_a = \frac{e^{-\Delta \bar{G}/kT}}{55.6}$ and $k_1 = N_1 k_2 \epsilon v$

Therefore k_1 and k_a , the adsorption constants, and N_1 in equation (1) can be calculated, using the following treatment and so $\Delta \bar{G}$, the free energy of counter ion binding, can be evaluated.

The Reversal of Charge and Log C- ζ Relationship

For large emulsion droplets (assumed to be spherical) of the present system, where particle radius is much larger than the double layer thickness ($Ka \gg 1$, K and a being respectively the Debye-Hückel parameter and radius of the particle), the charge density in the diffuse double layer is denoted by the expression⁸ :

$$\sigma_s = \frac{K \epsilon \Psi_\delta}{4\pi} \quad \text{or} \quad \Delta \sigma_s = K \epsilon \Delta \Psi_\delta / 4 \pi$$

where $\Delta \Psi_\delta$ is also given by the relation:

$$\Delta \Psi_\delta = \Psi_\delta^0 - \Psi_\delta = \frac{4 \pi}{K \epsilon} \cdot \frac{k_1 C}{1 + k_a C} \quad (2)$$

which directly relates Ψ_δ (Stern potential) with C , Ψ_δ^0 being constant. With continued adsorption, $\Delta \sigma_s$ may increase till Ψ_δ becomes zero and $\Delta \Psi_\delta = \Psi_\delta^0$. If the process of binding continues further, $\Delta \Psi_\delta > \Psi_\delta^0$ and therefore Ψ_δ has to be negative, thereby reversing the charge of the system.

Successive differentiation of equation (2) provides the following relationships⁷ between $\ln C$ and Ψ_δ :

$$\frac{d\Psi_\delta}{d \ln C} = - \frac{4 \pi}{K \epsilon} \cdot \frac{k_1 C}{(1 + k_a C)^2}$$

$$\frac{d^2 \Psi_\delta}{d \ln C^2} = \frac{4 \pi}{K \epsilon} \cdot \frac{k_1 (k_a C - 1)}{(1 + k_a C)^3}$$

6. Stern, *Z. Elektrochem.*, 1924, 30, 568.

7. Ottewill, et al., *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1960, 56, 854.

8. Verwey and Overbeek, "Theory of Stability of Lyophobic Colloids", Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1948, p. 38.

since at the zero point of charge, from equation (2) :

$$\Psi^{\circ}_\delta = \frac{4 \pi v e N_1 C k_2}{K \epsilon (1 + k_2 C)} \quad \text{i. e.} \quad \frac{1}{C} = \frac{4 \pi v e N_1 k_2}{K \epsilon \Psi^{\circ}_\delta} - k_2 \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

We have

$$\left(\frac{d \Psi_\delta}{d \ln C} \right) \Psi^{\circ}_\delta = 0 = \frac{K \epsilon}{4 \pi e v N_1} (\Psi^{\circ}_\delta)^2 - \Psi^{\circ}_\delta \quad (4)$$

which shows that at the zero point of charge, the slope of the $\log C - \zeta$ (assuming $\Psi^{\circ}_\delta = \zeta^{\circ}$) curve is independent of k_2 but does depend on Ψ°_δ , the valence of the adsorbed ions and N_1 . Equations (3) and (4) therefore have been used in the calculation of k_2 and N_1 , the values of the latter two quantities being utilised to calculate $\Delta \bar{G}$ and k_1 from equation (1)

EXPERIMENTAL

Petroleum (density 0.750g./ml at 20°; b.p. 120-60°) used in the emulsification was of A.R. (B.D.H.) quality. Its further purification was carried out by passing it through an alumina column. The continuous phase of the emulsions was double distilled water; the second distillation and storage were carried out in pyrex all-glass apparatus. BSA, the emulsifying agent, was a crystalline product of Armour Pharmaceutical Co. Ltd.

The emulsions were prepared by suspending 1.0% by volume of petroleum in a 0.01% solution of BSA in 0.01M-KCl and then emulsifying the mixture for half an hour with a homogenizer (Fisher Scientific Co., 14-497), having a stainless steel stirrer and a pyrex glass container. The emulsions were then allowed to stand for half an hour and the creamed layer was sucked off. Care was taken to prepare and sample all the emulsions under similar conditions.

Counting of the particles was done haemocytometrically, using an improved Neubauer model of a haemocytometer. About 750 particles were counted each time in 80 squares of a graticule fitted in the eye-piece (each square corresponding to a volume of 1.22×10^{-7} ml) with a Tally counter (Fisher Scientific Co., 7-903) under a Leitz microscope using 15×95 times magnification. A duplicate counting was always carried out with another sample and the mean of determinations was taken to calculate the particle concentration. The results were reproducible to 5.0%.

The pH of the system after adding the requisite inorganic cation was adjusted with the aid of a Pye universal pH-meter with an accuracy of 0.1 unit. Under normal conditions the pH of the emulsions was 5.6 ± 0.2 . The electrophoresis measurements were carried out with the help of a Mattson⁹ type pyrex-glass closed cylindrical microcell¹⁰⁻¹¹.

From the electrophoretic mobility ζ -potentials (to be identified with surface potentials of the emulsion droplets of 1.24 μ radius and charge densities $< 1.4 \times 10^4$ e.s.u./cm²

9. Mattson, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1933, 37, 223.

10. Bangham *et al.*, *Nature*, 1958, 182, 642.

11. Srivastava, Dissertation, Cambridge University, 1962, p. 9.

in the present investigation) were calculated using the Helmholtz¹²-Smoluchowski¹³ equation :

$$\zeta = \frac{4\pi\eta}{\epsilon} U$$

where ζ is the zeta-potential; η and ϵ are respectively the bulk viscosity and dielectric constant of the dispersion medium (water) and U is the electrophoretic mobility. The reproducibility of ζ -potentials was within ± 1.0 mv.

At a particular pH, corresponding to a certain ζ -potential, the extent of flocculation could be calculated from the formula :

$$D = \frac{\text{Number of doublets}}{\text{Number of doublets} + \text{number of singlets}}$$

where D is the number of particles associated with a specified particle, i.e., the degree of aggregation.

Variation of ζ with pH at Constant Concentration of the Counter Ion

The curves showing the electrophoretic behaviour of the standard BSA (0.01%) emulsion in 0.01M-KCl on the addition of small quantities of inorganic counter ions, such that the total ionic strength remains unaffected, are shown in Fig. 1 as a function of pH at a constant concentration of the added ion. In order to verify whether the effect observed was due to gegen ions or the neben ions, the curve for CuCl₂ was also obtained with CuSO₄ · 5H₂O at the same ionic strength, which showed no difference, thus indicating that the result was independent of the anionic species at the comparatively low concentrations used. It is evident that the effective species, the counter ions, i.e., the cations, become bound to the protein-coated emulsion droplets at all pH's between 4.5 and 6.0 and therefore render the ζ -potential more positive, depending on their valence. It is also clear that the tendency of the cation binding for a constant concentration increases with pH, it being appreciable even at pH 4.5 where the *pK* of the carboxyl groups of BSA is 3.4 and its maximum at pH 6.0. The position of the La³⁺-curve is rather peculiar although its concentration is in keeping with the Hardy and Schulze law. This has been discussed later.

Variation of ζ with the Concentration of the Cation at a Constant pH

The effect of the concentrations of the cations of different valencies on the electrophoretic properties of the BSA emulsion of three pH's, viz., 4.5, 5.5, and 6.0, is shown in Fig. 2 as ζ -log C curves. The form of these curves is, in general, according to the theoretical⁷ predictions, there being a tendency of the slope of the curve and therefore the adsorbability of the corresponding counter ion at virtually constant ionic strength to increase with its valence. At effectively constant ionic strengths, the increase in the positive ζ -potential within the pH range used is a clear indication of the fact that the cation-binding to the protein surface is occurring. Further, since the curves at pH 5.5 and 6.0 are steeper than those at pH 4.5, the extent of the binding is more in the previous case

12. Helmholtz, *Wied. Ann.*, 1879, 7, 337.

13. Smoluchowski, *Bull. Inter. Acad. Sci.*, Cracovie, 1903, 184.

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FIG. 1. Variation of ζ_0 -potential of the BSA emulsion at constant conc. of the counter ion.

FIG. 2. Charge reversal spectra of the BSA emulsion at pH 5.5 and 6.0 in presence of counter ions.

because of higher pK values of the carboxyl groups. The decrease in potentials at pH 5.5 and 6.0 is assigned to the specific adsorption of the ions in the Stern layer.

Flocculation Concentrations, the Reversal of Charge, and the Binding Constants

It was ascertained¹⁴ that some flocculation was occurring in the secondary minimum at pH 4.5, 5.5, and 6.0 even when just 0.01 M -KCl was present. The addition of the polyvalent cations only alters the degrees of aggregation by virtue of specific flocculation. Consequently, there is nothing like flocculation concentration of these cations for the present system. At pH 4.5, since the addition of the counter ion increases the ζ -potential, the degree of flocculation decreases and the emulsion becomes more stable. At pH 5.5 and 6.0, however, where a decrease of ζ -potential is occurring with the increase in the concentration of the cation, ultimately a stage is reached where the ζ becomes zero and the charge of the system is reversed, as already discussed theoretically.

FIG. 3. ζ -potential against log molar conc. of the added cation.

The reversal of charge is illustrated in Fig. 3, which shows the cation sequence in the order: $\text{Th}^{4+} > \text{Cu}^{2+} > \text{La}^{3+} > \text{Ca}^{2+} > \text{K}^+$. The place of La^{3+} in the series is again irregular.

14. Srivastava, Dissertation, Cambridge University, 1962, pp. 57, 71.

K^+ ions being monovalent do not bind to the protein surface appreciably and hence the charge reversal concentration is not reached at pH 5.5 and 6.0. At pH 4.5, however, the reversal of charge does occur at 0.1 M -KCl. This is an example of anion binding (Cl^-) as may be clearly seen from somewhat peculiar curve for charge reversal with KCl. In this case ζ -potential is initially + 10mv at 0.01 M -KCl¹⁴. With addition of KCl ($> 0.01M$), the ζ -potential decreases till at 0.1 M concentration; its sign is reversed and becomes negative. Further addition of KCl again increases ζ (now negative) due to the binding of Cl^- ions.

From the gradients of the curves (Fig. 2) at the zero point of charge, the different binding parameters, e.g., N_1 , the number of binding sites, k_1 and k_2 , the adsorption constants, and $\Delta'G$, the binding energies, have been calculated, using the relationship discussed (*vide supra*). The values obtained are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Binding parameters of cation adsorption.

Cation.	pH.	Charge reversal conc. (moles/litre).	k_2 .	k_1 .	$N_1 \times 10^{-12}$.	
					(Groups/cm ²).	(kcal./mole).
Ca	6.0	3.09×10^{-3}	1.06×10^2	5.30×10^5	5.15	5.0
..	5.5	1.99×10^{-3}	1.22×10^2	3.68×10^5	3.12	5.1
Cu	6.0	1.00×10^{-4}	2.43×10^3	1.38×10^7	5.90	6.8
..	5.5	0.50×10^{-4}	4.30×10^3	1.49×10^7	3.59	7.1
La	6.0	3.09×10^{-4}	0.94×10^3	4.35×10^6	3.20	7.6
..	5.5	2.00×10^{-4}	1.70×10^3	3.98×10^6	1.63	6.5
Th	6.0	8.00×10^{-6}	1.12×10^5	2.64×10^8	1.22	9.0
..	5.5	5.00×10^{-6}	2.60×10^5	2.86×10^8	0.54	9.5

It is interesting to observe from the above table that the values of k_1 , k_2 , N_1 , and $\Delta'G$ seem to depend on the pH of the emulsion as well.

Degrees of Aggregation

It has been already remarked that at pH 5.5 and 6.0, since the ζ -potentials of the system decrease with the increasing concentrations of the cation, the degrees of aggregation increase. On the contrary, at pH 4.5 a decrease of the degrees of aggregation takes place and hence the emulsion tends to be stable with increasing concentration. This last type of behaviour is also noticeable even at pH 5.5 and 6.0 in presence of a sufficient amount of the cation after the reversal of charge. Here degrees of aggregation have been found, however, only for limited ζ -potentials (Fig. 4) at pH 5.5 and 6.0. At the zero point of charge (e.g. for $3.0 \times 10^{-5} M$ La at pH 5.5, $1 \times 10^{-4} M$ Ca at pH 5.0, etc.) flocculation is almost instantaneous and it is not possible to calculate the degrees of aggregation. The results are recorded in Table II

TABLE II

Cation.	pH.	ζ .	Conc.	Degrees of aggregation.
Ca	6.0	12.7 mv	$1.00 \times 10^{-4} M$	9.8%
"	5.5	8.0	1.00×10^{-4}	20.0
La	6.0	13.1	1.00×10^{-5}	9.4
"	5.5	8.0	1.00×10^{-5}	20.0
Cu	6.0	7.6	1.25×10^{-5}	21.0
"	5.5	3.0	1.25×10^{-5}	..
Th	6.0	9.0	2.00×10^{-6}	20.0
"	5.5	3.0	2.00×10^{-6}	..

FIG. 4. Plot of ζ_t against time for calculation of the degree of aggregation.

DISCUSSION

The adsorbabilities of the counter ions at the surface of the protein-coated emulsion droplets, as denoted by the change of the Stern potential at practically constant ionic strength and as measured by k_s , reveal explicitly the specificity of the cations in binding, the value of k_s being highest for tetravalent Th^{4+} ions. The mean value of N_s , the maximum number of available sites (Table I), 3.04×10^{12} (the average of the means, 2.22×10^{12} at pH 5.5 and 6.0 respectively), corresponds to one charge per $3,290 \text{ \AA}^2$, which compares well with the value obtained (2.71×10^{12} groups/cm² or one charge per $3,700 \text{ \AA}^2$) by Wilkins and co-workers⁵ for the BSA-coated sheep leucocytes. The difference in the

values of N , at pH 5.5 and 6.0 is attributed to different pK values of the carboxyl groups of BSA.

The values of the energies of the cation binding also seem to be of the right order for the binding of the metallic ions at the ionogenic surface¹⁵. Thus the values of $-\Delta\bar{G}$ for Cu^{2+} , 6.8 and 7.1, fit well within the range of 4.39 to 7.3 kcal./mole obtained by Klotz¹⁶ for the binding of Cu^{2+} to various proteins. Further, since $\Delta\bar{G}$ can be separated into two constituents, viz., chemical and electrical,

$$\Delta\bar{G} = \Delta G + v e \Psi_{\delta}$$

where ΔG is the chemical free energy of adsorption and $v e \Psi_{\delta}$ is the electrical constituent, in view of the comparatively small negative potentials of the present system ($v e \Psi_{\delta} \ll \Delta G$), $\Delta\bar{G}$ may be regarded as reasonably constant and the Langmuir adsorption isotherm may be assumed to apply to the present system.

On comparing the standard Schulze-Hardy ratio 100:8.8:1.4 of flocculation values of divalent, trivalent, and tetravalent ions with the one obtained here, 100:3.24:10.03 (at pH 6.0) and 100:2.51:10.025 (at pH 5.5) for the charge reversal for Ca^{2+} : Cu^{2+} : La^{3+} : Th^{4+} , marked deviations are observed, which may be attributed to specific binding phenomena. The behaviour of La is remarkably abnormal (cf. Wilkins⁵) and may apparently be explained on the basis of its hydrolysis and free energies of hydration. Another probable explanation may be that if cross-linking is the operative mechanism in counterion binding, La^{3+} being trivalent cannot bind as easily as divalent copper.

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15. Edsall and Wyman, *J. Biophys. Chem.*, 1958, 1, 172.

16. Neurath and Bailey, "The Proteins", Academic Press, New York, 1953, vol. 1B, p. 727.